
Current Practices Of Acquisition Of E-Resources: A Study Of Academic Law Libraries Affiliated To Savitribai Phule Pune University Pune

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Abstract:

The paper presented on current practices of acquisition and management of e-resources in libraries of law colleges affiliated with Savitribai Phule Pune University, Pune. The survey method was used for the study with a structured questionnaire for librarians. The researcher has received 80.77% responses and the same data has been used for further analysis and interpretations. Research found that acquisition modes of e-resource by law college libraries with Independently (81%), and law college libraries subscribing e-resources from Direct from publisher (75%), followed by vendors (20%) and from aggregator (5%). Study found that major criteria for selection of e-resources was allocation and availability of budget by parent organization, followed by subject coverage (30%), and user feedback (15%), Subject: High impact research areas (10%), Trail Access (10%). The subscription model (57%) is the most preferable model among academic law college libraries followed by purchase of demand model (29%), sustainable of database ((57%), is the major problem being faced by the college libraries followed by lack of standard pricing model (14%) and procedure.

Keywords: Resources Acquisition, Modes of Acquisition, Academic Law Libraries, Savitribai Phule Pune University.

Introduction:

During past few decades, the library environment particularly the academic library environment has undergone drastic change in-terms of collection, services and role of Library and Information Science Professionals. “The availability of IT based electronic resources has exerted ever-increasing pressures on libraries and there is no doubt that e-resources are expanding rapidly. However, the e-resources have

proved their importance due to their merits like, communication, sharing, space consuming, time consuming, multi-access etc. Hence, day by day the utility and popularity of e-resources is visible in the procurement. However, in order to meet the ever-increasing demand of the user community in a digital environment, libraries have to develop ways to manage access to materials available in electronic format and to effectively share them much as they have shared print resources for

over a century through inter library lending” (Devi & Devi, 2005).

Need and Importance of the Study:

Considering importance of law library collection development with reference to electronic material and changing structure of legal system and the working of judicial fraternity. It is essential to understand the latest updates on law librarianship. Thus, researcher thought to carry out a study `Current Practices of Acquisition and Management of e-Resources: A Study of Academic Law Libraries affiliated to Savitribai Phule Pune University Pune

Literature Review:

Most of the literature in this area is devoted to the use of and impact of e-resources specifically in the academic libraries and very less research is found with respect to academic law libraries. Very little research found on current practices and criteria related to online databases.

(Landesman, 2005) Authors have given introductory of e-resources collection development and the process of collection which they have given could be applied for developing e-resources.

Kaur & Walia, (2016) Study examined the current practices related to e-resource collection development in management libraries of India with special reference to the National Capital Region (NCR) of Delhi with some constructive suggestions for improvement in this area.

(Khan & Bhatti, 2016) Study discovers the factors which effect collection development and management in academic libraries. It provides an overview of various factors that influence collection development activities in the academic libraries. It provides an insight

for the selectors of library resources to take these factors into account for building effective collections in the academic libraries of Pakistan and abroad.

R. Kaur & Gaur, (2017) Researcher has focused on collection development needs and trends by considering ICT impact on libraries. He also stressed on e-resources challenges and policies of collection development in the paper.

Wadekar & Nagarkar, (2018) The purpose of this paper was to know-how the university libraries are managing online databases, especially from the Maharashtra state of India. The focus was to study the difficulties and challenges faced by the university librarians.

Mwilongo et al., (2020) Study has suggested valuable recommendation for establishment of collection development policies as they will guide to LIS professionals to develop collection in a systematic way. Further, it emphasized on required skills and upgradation for library professionals in order to effectively manage with hybrid collection.

After browsing literature available, it was found that there is no study conducted yet on Current Practices of Electronic Resource Management: A Study of Academic Law Libraries affiliated to Savitribai Phule Pune University Pune. Therefore, Researcher thought to carry out this study.

Objectives:

1. To study the different modes of procurement and acquisition of e-resources in academic law libraries affiliated to SPPU.
2. To examine the different criteria for selection of e-resources and;

3. To find out the preference of acquisition model for acquiring electronic resources.
4. To identify the mode of access for e-resources/legal databases.
5. To identify problems associated with the e-resources and collection development in libraries

Scope:

The present study is limited to academic law college's libraries affiliated to Savitribai Phule Pune University, Pune (SSPU). The target population is 26 law college libraries considered for the present study. Below is the list of law colleges chronologically arranged according to year of inceptions.

Academic Law Colleges comes under Savitribai Phule Pune University, Pune

Sr. No.	Name of Law Colleges	Est. Year
1	ILS Law College Pune	1924
2	Ahmednagar Jilha Maratha Vidya Prasarak Samaj's New Law College, Ahmednagar	1970
3	N B Thakur Law College, Nashik	1970
4	Karmaveer Bhausaheb Hire Law College Malegaon Camp, Tal Malegaon Dist - Nashik	1971
5	Yashwantrao Chavan Law College, Pune	1978
6	New Law Academy, Pune	1994
7	Kha Shri Govindrao Adik Law College Shirampur	1998
8	Shri. Omkarnath Malpani Law College Sangamner	1998
9	Navjeevan Law College, Nashik	1999
10	Vidya Pratishthans Vasanttrao Pawar Law College Baramati	1999
11	Dr. D. Y. Patil Law College, Pune	2001

12	Abhinav Education society's Law college Ambegaon, Pune.	2003
13	Balaji Law college, Pune	2003
14	MMM's Shankarrao Chavan Law College, Pune	2003
15	PES Modern Law College, Pune	2003
16	Shri Shivaji Maratha Society's Law College, Pune	2003
17	Sinhgad Law College, Pune	2003
18	PDEA's Law College, Hadapsar	2004
19	Deccan Education Society Shri Navalmal Firodia Law College Pune	2004
20	Maratha Vidya Prasarak Samaj M.V.P.Samaj's Law College Nashik	2004
21	Hutatma Rajguru Shikshan Prasarak Mandal's Sarsenapati Hambirrao Mohite Law College, Rajgurunagar	2007
22	Kopergaon Taluka Vidyarthi Sahayyak Samiti Sw.Shri.Namdevrao Parjane Patil Law College	2007
23	SNBP Law College, Pune	2009
24	C.D.Deshmukh Law College, Ahmednagar	2012
25	Army Law College, Pune	2018
26	Mahatma Gandhi Vidyamandir Samajshri Prashantdada Hiray Law College Nashik	2018

Research Methodology:

To fulfill the objectives of the present study a Survey method was used with the questionnaire (Librarian) as tool for data collection. Survey is systematic way of collecting data from samples.

Online questionnaire distributed through emails and collected data through google form and downloaded spreadsheet for further analysis.

DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION:

SAMPLE RESPONSES:

Table No. 1 reveal that out of 26 respondents, researcher received 80.77% responses. It is sufficient for the further data analysis and interpretations.

Total Law Colleges Libraries	Responses	Responses in %
26	21	80.77

Table No. 1 Responses in Percentages

Modes of Subscription of E-Resources:

Acquisition modes of e-resources is an essential part of collection development of e-resources. This is very tedious task specially with reference to legal databases and foreign e-journals. Different libraries follow different modes of subscription. Information from twenty-one academic law libraries was sought on mode for acquisition of e-resources. Figure Number 1 reveals that acquisition of e-resource by Independently (81%), and Both- Independently and Consortia (14%), followed by consortia (5%). Here it is clear that most of the law libraries are subscribing through independently.

Here, researcher has tried to investigate further by asking how does libraries are subscribing e-resources. Graph No. 2 reveal that Direct from publisher (75%), from vendor (20%) and from aggregator (5%).

Graph No. 1: Modes of acquiring e-resources

Graph No. 2: If Independent, how does your library subscribe

Criteria for Selection of Any E-Resources/Databases:

Role of any academic library is to acquire information resources in support teaching and research activities. Selection of e-resources done on the basis of subject: high impact research areas, Subject coverage, User feedback, Trail access and Availability of Budget. The library will give priority to acquiring e-resources which gives the return on investment. Graph No. 3 reveals that the criteria for Budget: Availability and Allocation of Budget (35%), Coverage (30%), User

feedback (15%), Subject: High impact research areas (10%), Trail Access (10%)

Graph No. 3: Criteria for selection of any e-resources/databases

Preference Model For Acquisition Of Legal Databases:

Graph No. 4 reveals that preference models for acquisition of e-resources/legal databases. Subscription model (57%), Purchase of demand model (29%), Perpetual access model (9%), Patron driven acquisition model (5%). It means that subscription model is preferable model for subscription of e-resources among academic law libraries.

Graph No. 4: Preference model for acquisition of legal databases

Mode Of Access For E-Resources/Legal Databases:

Mode of access is essential component for optimum use of subscribed e-resources/databases. Until and unless e-resources are not been accessible by 24/7

from anywhere. then limitation will be arisen and ultimately, we may not achieve the return on investment. Therefore, researcher has tried to understand the method of access given for e-resources from respondent's libraries. Below Graph No. 5 depicted the mode access from IP based (43%), and Remote Access (57%). It means that most of the libraries are giving access from remotely. but still others (43%) libraries should make it accessible remotely as it will enhance the usage of resources.

Graph No. 5: Mode of access for e-resources/legal databases

Problems During Subscription Of Legal Database:

Researcher has tried to identify what kind of problems being faced by the law college libraries during subscription of e-resources/legal databases. Graph No. 5 reflects that sustainable of database (57%), Lack of standard procedure (14%), Lack of standard pricing (14%), other problems (15%). It means that sustainable of database is the major problem being faced by the college libraries followed by lack of standard pricing model and procedure.

Graph No. 6: Problems during subscription of legal database

Major Findings:

1. Researcher has received 80.77% responses from the law college librarians.
2. Study found that acquisition of e-resource by college libraries with Independently (81%), and Both-Independently and Consortia (14%), followed by consortia (5%). Here, it is clear that most of the law libraries are subscribing through independently.
3. Addition study found that most of the law college libraries subscribing e-resources from Direct from publisher (75%), followed by vendors (20%) and from aggregator (5%).
4. Research found that major criteria for selection of e-resources was allocation and availability of budget by parent organization, followed by subject coverage (30%), and user feedback (15%), Subject: High impact research areas (10%), Trail Access (10%).
5. Subscription model (57%) is the most preferable model among academic law college libraries followed by purchase of demand model (29%), the, Perpetual access model (9%), Patron driven acquisition model (5%).

6. Study found that mode access for e-resources from IP based (43%), and Remote Access (57%). It means that most of the libraries are giving access from remotely, but still others (43%) libraries should make it accessible remotely as it will enhance the usage of resources.
7. Study found that that sustainable of database ((57%), is the major problem being faced by the college libraries followed by lack of standard pricing model (14%) and procedure.

Conclusions:

Today the libraries of law colleges are re-orienting their collections and collection development policies in the light of e-resources. "The important goal of each library is to provide correct, updated and authentic information to the users, by adopting the 'e-resource acquisition policy' successfully. Thus, by adopting e-resource acquisition policy, all the principles laid down by Dr. S.R. Ranganathan regarding Laws of Library Science are followed." (Sinha & Gautam, 2015) The finding of study reveals that tools and criteria used for selecting e-resources are different from those used printed resources. In the case of printed materials, the acquisition librarian makes decision to acquire an item with only limited consultation with the other departments following established policies and guidelines. Unlike print material, the acquisition librarian cannot make a decision to acquire an e-resources isolation. He/she should coordinate closely with various departments to evaluate the suitability of e-resource prior to decision to acquire. Study reveals that budget allocation from parent organization is an

important for procurement of electronic material and law librarians are trying to develop the collection on the basis of subject coverage and related material which associated with programs offered by law colleges. Standard pricing models should be done by the publishers as the same problems being faced by the college libraries, found in the study.

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